

THE STUDY OF PHYSICAL FITNESS PARAMETERS ON FEMALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

The intention of this study is to reveal the effect of physical fitness parameters on female volleyball players in the age group of 16 to 18 years. In this study, a total of 12 female players from SDM sports hostel, Ujire, Mangalore participated. Anthropometric and physical fitness measurements were recorded and analyzed. To be specific, age, height and weight were taken for anthropometric profile and for physical fitness profile, explosive strength measurements were taken. In addition to that, endurance and agility tests were also documented. A 12 minute endurance run and 4x10 m shuttle run test for both endurance and agility tests were conducted respectively. The recorded data was interpreted to determine the physical fitness of the players.

Keywords: Physical fitness, volleyball.

INTRODUCTION

One of the important factors of a professional volleyball player is the physical fitness. Different tests are conducted to conclude the physical fitness of the player. Endurance run, agility run, jump and reach height test, balance and flexibility are few of the tests [1]. The extreme volleyball activities include repeated jumping and throwing activities [2]. To perform all these activities, one should have a good anthropometric profile [3, 4 and 5]. Having all desired anthropometric measurements is not enough to call a player as a physical fit volleyball player. One should also pass through the tests of muscular strength, explosive strength, speed, flexibility and balance [6]. The objective of the present study is to analyse different physical fitness capabilities, explosive strength and finally, the impact of all the anthropometric and physical fitness parameters on the female volleyball players.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND DISCUSSION

The female student players of SDM sports hostel, Ujire from Mangalore (under 18 category-female) were taken into consideration for our study. To know the explosive strength of volleyball players, each one of the players were investigated with standing reach height

and Jump-reach height (both measured in metres) in addition to their age (years), height (in centimetre) and weight (in kilogram).

Table I: The Anthropometric and Physical fitness measurements of female volleyball players.

Players No.	Age (yrs)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Explosive Strength		Endurance -12 min run (in meters)	Agility – shuttle run 4x10m (in seconds : microseconds)
				Standing Reach (in m)	Jump and Reach (in m)		
1	18	154	43	2.03	2.31	1650	12:85
2	17	166	56	2.18	2.45	3860	12:41
3	17	169	52	2.25	2.51	3930	12:52
4	16	169	58	2.24	2.56	4150	11:88
5	17	165	50	2.18	2.44	2040	12:68
6	18	169	51	2.24	2.50	2000	12:31
7	16	152	44	1.96	2.19	1650	12:96
8	18	170	51	2.22	2.48	1650	13:42
9	16	155	42	2.04	2.28	1920	13:47
10	18	171	57	2.33	2.64	4240	11:86
11	16	161	46	2.12	2.34	2650	12:43
12	17	167	55	2.23	2.46	2040	12:76

After getting the basic anthropometric measurements and explosive strength height measurements, endurance and agility tests were conducted. In endurance test, a 12 minute run was conducted. In agility test, a shuttle run of 4x10 m run was conducted. All the above anthropometric and physical fitness measurements were taken as per the rules and regulations. Table I shows the anthropometric and physical fitness measurements of 12 female volleyball players.

From the data collected, one crucial interpretation can be made. Players with the highest anthropometric profile measurements are showing good explosive strength, phenomenal endurance and agility capabilities. With the highest explosive strengths (0.32 m and 0.31 m), achieving longest distances in 12 minute endurance run (4150 m and 4240 m) and a impressive agile profile achieved in 4x10 m shuttle run (11:88 and 11:86 in s:µs), it is quite easy to say the player no. 4 and 10 are the ones to have a perfect physical fitness profile. From the table 1, highlighted readings of two players, player no. 4 and player no. 10, are having a healthy anthropometric profile and also a desirable physical fitness.

CONCLUSION

Physical fitness of a player influences the sports career span. In order to have a good physical fitness profile, a player has to begin the preparation work with building a good anthropometric profile and maintaining it. When all the parameter values of fitness and anthropometric measurements come in the optimal range, then a player can feel safe to undergo volleyball training activities. Even minor injuries can be minimised and avoided if the player is having a healthy physical fitness profile.

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